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KANGAROO MOTHER CARE (KMC) FOR DEVELOPPING COUNTRIES

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Brief Introduction: Low Birth Weight (LBW) is either the direct or an associated cause in nearly 60% of the 4'000.000 children's deaths occurring annually worldwide. KMC is an evidence-based technology useful for ameliorating LBW effects on infant mortality and morbidity. Since more than 10 years the objective of the Kangaroo Foundation was 1)To evaluate efficacy and safety of KMC 2)To explore means for transference, adaptation and acceptance of KMC to other settings mainly in the developing world 3)To evaluate the degree of successful dissemination, permanence and performance of local and regional KMC programs in different countries

Materials & Methods: In a first phase, safety and efficacy of KMC was demonstrated by a set of clinical studies (Cohort, RCT). Second phase consists of an ongoing: 1)Dissemination of KMC to other institutions of developing countries by training health-care teams not only in KMC but in recording and monitoring of key-quality indicators 2)Coaching of new KMC teams while implementing and adapting their programs, 3)Design and implementation of a quality assurance program to support a continuous performance evaluation (KMC network) 4)Identification and analysis of difficulties encountered in other settings for the implementation of KMC.

Candidates for KMC training are multidisciplinary health-care teams mainly from crowded cities' hospitals in developing countries, willing to try interventions to improve LBW survival and quality of life, to rationalize resources use and to humanize neonatal care. Institutions willing to teach others are favored.

Clinical Cases or Summary Results: We trained 60 teams from 30 countries since 1994. In 80% of teams trained in Bogota, KMC implementation has been successful, despite specific needs and difficulties encountered by each program in each setting. Various KMC programs already began a national KMC training diffusion program in their countries. The 3 components of KMC: kangaroo position, early discharge with KMC follow up and breastfeeding had been adapted to local circumstances, patients needs and care scenario: NICU, intermediate care, ambulatory care with home discharge in kangaroo position. Early discharge and KMC ambulatory follow-up clinic is the most difficult aspect of KMC to implement, despite its significant impact on hospital costs and risks. Major difficulties to many newly established programs are insufficient access to the network, to scientific literature on KMC and insufficient local research capability.

Conclusions: Our experience shows the feasibility of developing a complex effective and efficient healthcare intervention in a developing country, and direct transfer to developing countries through training, coaching, support and development of non-governmental networks.

Keywords: Kangaroo Mother Care, developing countries, premature infant

Presenter: Eleonora Rodriguez

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MODIFICATION OF CERVICAL LENGTH AFTER CERVICAL PESSARY INSERTION AND ITS

CORRELATION WITH WEEKS OF GESTATION

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Brief Introduction: The aim of this study was to observe the modifications of the cervical length (CL) after insertion of a cervical pessary (Arabin® ASQ 65/25/32) in patients obtained from the PECEP Trial and also measure the correlation of this modification with the weeks of gestation (WG) at birth, compared with the expectant management group.

Materials & Methods: Randomised prospective study of 380 asymptomatic risk-free singleton pregnancies between weeks 20+0 and 23+6. CL in all patients was short (<25 mm) and they were randomised into two groups: expectant management and cervical pessary. Cervical length was measured in all patients after pessary insertion and before 24+0 WG.

Clinical Cases or Summary Results: The study included 380 pregnant women: 190 underwent periodic controls of CL (expectant management) and 190 were fitted with a pessary. Mean CL in both groups at the time of randomisation showed no statistically-significant differences (pessary group: 19.02 mm and management group: 19.00 mm; $p=0.966$). Mean CL measured after randomisation and before 24+0 WG was 15.44 mm in patients of the expectant management group and 21.56 mm in the pessary group. These differences were statistically significant ($p=0.000$). When means at randomisation and at the second measurement were compared, LC had decreased by 3.58 mm in the expected management group and increased by 2.56 mm in the pessary group; this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$). Coefficients of correlation showed that in patients with the same CL at 20 WG in both groups, those with a pessary gave birth later. In the expectant management group, a correlation was found between the size of the decrease in CL between 20 WG and later measurement and WG at delivery. However, an increase in CL after pessary insertion did not correlate with an increase in WG at birth.

Conclusions: Insertion of an Arabin cervical pessary increased CL in asymptomatic patients with a short cervix

Asymptomatic patients with a short cervix at week 20 who received expectant management presented a decrease in CL as WG increased, which correlated with shorter WG at birth

The cervical pessary stabilises the progressive decrease in CL, which correlated with longer WG at birth

The increase in CL after cervical pessary insertion did not correlate with an increase in WG at birth

Keywords: cervical length, cervical pessary, preterm birth

Presenter: Manel Mendoza

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PREDICTIVE VALUES OF SERUM MARKERS OF OXIDATIVE STRESS AND PAPP-A IN PRETERM DELIVERIES

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Brief Introduction: Preterm delivery in contemporary world presents the most common complication in pregnancy which is also the main cause of perinatal mortality. Multiple studies showed that oxidative stress, balance disorder between defense antioxidative systems and production of free oxygen radicals respectively, may jeopardize any stage of intrauterine development and eventually lead to the preterm delivery with complications in premature babies like bronchopulmonary dysplasia, intraventricular hemorrhage, necrotizing enterocolitis and other.

The aim of this study was to confirm if early determination of markers of oxidative stress and PAPP-A in first trimester of pregnancy could identify pregnant women with increased risk for occurrence of preterm delivery.

Materials & Methods: The study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology in Novi Sad. Women were divided into two groups. Control group ($n=94$): pregnant women who delivered after 37+1 week of gestation (WG) with good outcome. Study group ($n=56$): pregnant women who delivered before 34.WG, singleton pregnancies without genetic anomalies of fetus. From all women in the period between 11. and 14. WG, anamnestic, anthropometric, demographic and socioeconomic data that could have an effect on the occurrence of preterm delivery were taken. All women underwent clinical, obstetrical and ultrasound examination as well as laboratory blood tests for determination of serum markers of oxidative stress superoxide dismutase (SOD), total antioxidative status (TAS), glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) and protein PAPP-A.

Clinical Cases or Summary Results: Women of the study group (31.81 ± 3.44) were on average older than women of the control group (29.31 ± 4.92). In the study group there were more smokers (14.2%) than in the control group (8.5%). BMI was approximately equal in both groups, while frequency of infections (bacterial vaginosis, cervical bacterial infections, urinary tract infections) was higher in the study group (21.3%) than in the control group (14.2%). There is no significant difference between women regarding the application of therapy in pregnancy (utrogestan and progesterone), while the number of previous pregnancies (more than two pregnancies) was higher in the study group (19.5%) than in the control group (10.4%). Markers of oxidative stress SOD and GSH-Px were statistically significant higher in the study group ($p < 0.05$), while the values of TAS were equal in both groups ($p = 0.26$). Values of PAPP-A were higher in the study (1.54 ± 0.33) than in the control group (1.59 ± 0.95).

Conclusions: Combining maternal risk factors with markers of oxidative stress SOD and GSH-Px and protein PAPP-A it is possible to create stratification of risk for selection of women to whom more attention to the increased possibility of preterm delivery will be given.

Keywords: preterm deliveries, oxidative stress, PAPP-A

Presenter: M. Bogavac

ID 061

EARLY DETECTION OF CARDIAC DYSFUNCTION AFTER PRETERM BIRTH BY 2D-SPECKLE-TRACKING ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY

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Brief Introduction: Preterm birth is associated with adverse cardiovascular events later in life. The underlying mechanisms are unknown.

We undertook a sequential analysis of cardiac function after preterm birth by speckle-tracking echocardiography (STE) and compared the results to a healthy control group.

Materials & Methods: Evaluation of cardiac function of 25 very preterm infants (GA 26–30 weeks) at birth, at term-equivalent age and at 3 months of corrected age and comparison to the findings in 30 healthy term children (1st investigation intrauterine). We measured longitudinal strain (%), strain rate (1/sec) and tissue velocities (cm/s) in both ventricles in systole and diastole to characterize myocardial performance and compared the results to conventional echocardiography.

Clinical Cases or Summary Results: At 3 months of corrected age, very preterm infants exhibit significantly lower left ventricular (LV) strain values (19.9 vs 22.0%, $p < 0.001$), systolic (5.8 vs 6.4 cm/s, $p = 0.01$) and diastolic (7.8 vs 10.6 cm/s, $p < 0.001$) tissue velocities and early diastolic strain-rate values (3.9/s vs 4.7/s, $p < 0.001$) compared to healthy control infants born at term. There was a trend to lower values even in the right ventricle- though not statistically significant.

Conclusions: Left ventricular systolic and diastolic dysfunction emerges already 6 months after very preterm birth and can be identified by STE while conventional echocardiography is not able to detect abnormal myocardial performance at this age. LV dysfunction might occur because of premature adaptation towards higher systemic afterload and incomplete re-modelling of the LV early in life.

Keywords: preterm, echocardiography, speckle-tracking

Presenter: U. Schubert

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EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL USE OF MAGNESIUM SULFATE FOR CEREBRAL PALSY PREVENTION.

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Brief Introduction: The aim of this study is to evaluate the implementation of a clinical protocol for the use of magnesium for cerebral palsy prevention, focusing on uptake, indications and safety. **Materials & Methods:** This retrospective and uncentred study included all women with fetuses of gestational age < 33 weeks whose birth was planned or expected within 24 hours from September 2011 (starting of implementation of magnesium sulfate in our department) to December 2012. We assigned women to receive magnesium sulfate, administered intravenously as a 4g bolus followed by a constant infusion of 1g per hour. If delivery had not occurred after 12 hours and was no longer considered imminent, the infusion was discontinued. The primary study outcome was to assess the rate of pre-delivery administration of magnesium sulfate over this time period.

Clinical Cases or Summary Results: Among the 5610 patients who delivered during the study period, 119 were eligible for the protocol. 68.1% of eligible gravidas received magnesium sulfate before delivery. In 2011, at the beginning of magnesium sulfate implementation, 76% of eligible gravidas received magnesium before delivery. The mean gestational age of the protocol's implementation was 30 weeks +/- 2 days. The mean duration of magnesium sulfate treatment was 289 +/- 398 minutes. Bolus and constant infusion were